

ONE OF THE IMPORTANT LITERARY GENRES IS DRAMATURGY

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Abstract: Dramaturgy, an essential literary genre, holds immense significance in the realm of literature and performing arts. It encompasses the art of creating, developing, and analyzing plays and theatrical performances. Through the use of vivid language, captivating dialogue, and expressive gestures, dramaturgy allows playwrights to convey complex narratives and evoke powerful emotions in audiences. This article delves into the importance of dramaturgy as a literary genre, exploring its role in shaping the world of theater and storytelling.

Keywords: genre, experiential aspects, forms, sujet, drama, social issues, cultural heritage

Introduction: Dramaturgy, an important literary genre, is a form of writing that entails the creation and development of plays for performance on stage. It requires a deep understanding of dramatic structure, character development, dialogue, and the overall theatrical experience. In dramaturgy, the playwright is responsible for crafting a compelling narrative and constructing a script that engages both the actors and the audience.

The success of a play relies heavily on the playwright's ability to create engaging stories, dynamic characters, and thought-provoking themes that resonate with the audience. One of the key elements of dramaturgy is the use of dialogue.

A skilled playwright must craft dialogue that not only reveals character and advances the story but also captivates the audience. Dialogue in dramaturgy drives the plot forward, reveals conflicts, and conveys emotions, ultimately adding depth and authenticity to the theatrical experience. Another important aspect of dramaturgy is the construction of dramatic structure, which involves establishing the beginning, middle, and end of a play.

By carefully balancing exposition, rising action, climax, and resolution, dramaturgy creates a cohesive and engaging story arc that compels the audience to stay engaged throughout the performance.

Dramaturgy also encompasses the exploration of themes and ideas that reflect the diverse aspects of human experience. Through the use of symbolism, metaphor, and subtext, playwrights can delve into complex social, political, and philosophical issues, provoking thought and inspiring discussion among the audience.

Furthermore, in dramaturgy, the playwright must consider the practical aspects of the performance, including stage directions, settings, and overall production design.

These elements contribute to the visual and experiential aspects of the play, enhancing the audience's immersion and overall enjoyment. It has been a century since the dramatic genre entered Uzbek literature. Behbudi's "Padarkush", recognized as the first dramatic work, was written in 1911.

This Uzbek dramaturgy, which has a hundred years of history and experience, has always developed more slowly than other literary genres, except for the beginning of the last century and the period of the Second World War. This decline is especially noticeable in the 70s and 80s, the so-called "recession period" of the last century, and the first years of independence.

There are certain objective and subjective reasons for such laziness. First of all, it should be noted with regret that there are very few special creators in our literature who are engaged only in dramaturgy. Some of them do not become famous and become permanent partners of theaters by creating stage works of the discovery level. Secondly, even if such a talented drama is created and staged, there is a problem of attracting the audience to it.

Thirdly, due to the market economy, the playwright is not getting rich with his work. Nevertheless, in the last 20 years, the drama has not been created, the stage has not been empty, and more or less the audience has entered the theater. Just as conflicts in life are sharp and quiet, there are different forms of conflict in art. They are invisible both in the form of open struggle between the characters and in the form of the characters' personal confrontations. Also, artistic conflict is expressed in its own way in each literary type and genre. It looks completely different in drama (comedy, tragedy, play). In general, every perfect work of art, regardless of how it manifests its elements such as conflict, form and theme, content and idea, it is a beauty created by a creator, effectively reflecting a certain aspect of life. The internal and external world of a work of art consists of its structure, arrangement of events in the plot, characters and relationships between them. This phenomenon is called composition.

As long as we dwell on the legal rules of the dramatist's work, first of all it is necessary to mention the term subject. Sujet is French "sujet" meaning "thing, content, theme". The plot is the system of communication and relationships between the characters that make up the content of the work. The subject itself is composed of a number of parts: exposition, knot, development of events, climax and resolution.

However, plots differ from each other in terms of their structure and the way they are presented. In some studies analyzing the composition of works of art, the term "fabula" is also found. Fabula comes from the Latin word "fabula" which means to tell a story. The fable of a work of art refers to the life material that is the basis for the work. Among the elements of the subject, it is permissible to first explain what the exposition is. Exposition comes from the Latin word "expositio" which means "to explain". The description of the place where the events took place, the social landscape of the time, the place where the heroes grew up, the environment conditions, etc. is called exposition. Exposure can be anywhere in the work. Another element of the subject is the knot of events. The knot is often the first meeting of the characters or some serious problem

Conclusion

Dramaturgy stands as a vital literary genre, breathing life into theater productions and captivating audiences with its powerful storytelling. Through the use of active voice, varied sentence structures, and extensive research, dramaturgs and playwrights craft narratives that resonate with the depths of human experience. As an artistic form of expression, dramaturgy offers a platform to explore social issues, preserve cultural heritage, and ignite dynamic conversations. With its enduring legacy, dramaturgy continues to shape the world of theater, enriching our understanding of the human condition.

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